

MILITARY PATRIOTIC EDUCATION - A COMPONENT PART OF SPIRITUAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article presents formation of our young people with intellectual potential, loyal to their country, the President, brave, brave and of course, healthy generation, forming in them the skills and competences of organizing defense in emergency situations and high moral and ethical qualities, the current in accordance with the principle of the interdependence and inseparability of education and upbringing of modern pedagogy, military-patriotic education is closely related to military pedagogical education.

Key words: military-technical training, comprehension, demonstration, system, unusual situation, physical training, creativity, discipline.

The military-pedagogical process is a complex social phenomenon. Its essence is determined by the purposeful organizational and educational activities of commanders, chiefs, educators to prepare military specialists, units and units to protect the country from armed aggression, to successfully conduct combat operations in the conditions of modern warfare. Forming our young people with intellectual potential, loyal to their country and President, brave and of course healthy generation is one of the urgent issues of today. The subject of "Pre-call up military education" allows students to deeply understand their constitutional rights and obligations regarding the protection of the Motherland, to create a foundation for fulfilling their honorable duty to protect their Motherland from any armed aggression, to increase their interest in the military profession, and and making correct and quick decisions in unexpected situations, as well as protecting oneself and loved ones in emergency situations, forming ideological immunity against internal and external threats, improving theoretical and practical knowledge and skills in the military field, Armed Forces includes very important and necessary tasks, such as preparing to serve in the ranks. In the implementation of this urgent process, the training of future teachers in the field of "Pre-call up military education" at the faculties of military education shows that our country pays great attention to this field.

To interest students in the military profession, to form their ability to consciously choose the military field, to help them acquire a certain military specialty, to reveal the nature of the officer's profession and the strict discipline and high requirements for it. is the basis. When guiding young students in the general secondary education, academic lyceum and professional education systems to the military field, first of all, the military-professional competence of the teacher of primary training before the draft should be at a high level.

We have determined that it is possible to develop military-professional competence as a result of the formation of certain abilities through the requirements for each subject taught to the primary teacher before the upcoming recruitment.

First of all, we set as one of our main tasks the analysis of the didactic possibilities of the subjects aimed at developing the military-professional competence of the pre-primary teacher before the upcoming call in the block of general vocational subjects.

It was found that "Military patriotism education" in the block of multi-professional subjects is one of the main subjects in the development of military-professional competence of primary teachers before the upcoming call-up.

The concept of military-patriotic education is defined in the "Brief Explanatory Dictionary of Military Terms" as follows: "Military-patriotic education is a component of spiritual education. Its ideological and theoretical basis is citizens' understanding of their duties and responsibilities for the security of our independent Motherland. Military-patriotic education is aimed at forming love for the Motherland, loyalty to the traditions of the Armed Forces, loyalty to the President of Uzbekistan, respect for laws and regulations, and other qualities."

The theoretical foundations of the science of military-patriotic education, the structural structure of the existing system for its implementation, the purpose, methodological foundations, content and essence, tasks, tools, pedagogical and psychological foundations, forms, methods, main processes, their stages, practical, includes methodological, organizational and other issues. To increase the effectiveness of military-patriotic education by scientifically studying, analyzing, and developing scientific conclusions and recommendations on the specific characteristics of these issues.

The purpose of the science of military-patriotic education is to realize readiness to serve in the defense of the Motherland. The realization of this goal implies the preparation of young people for the protection and defense of the Motherland, the formation of skills and qualifications for defense in emergency situations, as well as high moral and ethical qualities.

Military-patriotic education is also closely related to military-patriotic education in accordance with the principle of interdependence and inseparability of education and training in modern pedagogy. It is known that any education is carried out on the basis of acquiring relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities. This shows that the implementation of education, first of all, begins with the knowledge related to that education, that is, the educational process. In order to raise and educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism in the future, it is necessary for the primary teacher to make extensive use of the scientific principles, ways of development, effective forms and methods of the science of "Military-patriotic education" before the upcoming convocation.

The main didactic principles of the implementation of the science of "military-patriotic education" are scientificity, relevance to life, comprehensibility, demonstrability, consistency, etc. In order to be a patriot, it is necessary to first develop and educate knowledge, morality, love, and faith. For this, it is necessary to teach knowledge about patriotism, and to implement military-patriotic education, along with them, it is necessary to teach knowledge about military work.

In the course of our research, we determined the formation of the following skills and personal qualities related to the development of the military-professional competence of the pre-service teacher in mastering the subject "Military-patriotic education":

➤ On spiritual, moral and spiritual preparation:

- the confidence of the preparatory teacher until the upcoming call that the military power of our Armed Forces, which is the guarantee of the independence of our country, is

created by the work of everyone and in order to further strengthen it, in-depth knowledge, skills and qualifications, creative activity, discipline and high work ability are necessary. formed;

- develops duty, responsibility, patriotism, hatred of the enemy, high sensitivity and other social feelings.

- consciously understands the difficulties and hardships he may encounter in a real combat situation;

- acquires the skills to get used to the conditions of military activity and combat team;

- the experience of overcoming mental and physical difficulties improves;

- Legal and political preparation:

- awareness of the foreign and domestic policy of the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the reforms being carried out to strengthen the country's defense and the Armed Forces;

- the ability to unconditionally comply with the requirements of the general military regulations and the orders of the pedagogue-officers, control one's own behavior;

- willingness to comply with military disciplinary standards and requirements under any circumstances;

- to understand one's constitutional rights and obligations, to know the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, about the defense of the Motherland and its protection from armed aggression;

- On military-technical training:

- to know the importance of scientific and technical development and its impact on military work, the high requirements for studying modern combat equipment and weapons;

- to have the ability to transfer general technical skills and qualifications to situations of military-technical activity;

- to have the skills to use military weapons in field training and to act accurately in the performance of tasks;

- On practical and physical training::

- general physical qualities associated with the task of protecting the homeland - development of strength, speed, agility and endurance;

- having special physical qualities: ability to cope with dizziness, mountain sickness, movement in hot regions, limited water consumption, ability to move with special equipment and tools;

- willingness to comply with military disciplinary standards and requirements under any circumstances;

- by practicing military-practical sports, they acquire abilities such as the ability to overcome great physical load and stress;

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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